

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 24

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 24

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 24:1 The ^aearth is the LORD'S, and ¹all it contains, The ^bworld, and those who dwell in it. ² For He has ^afounded it upon the seas And established it upon the rivers. ³ Who may ^aascend into the ^bhill of the LORD? And who may stand in His holy ^cplace? ⁴ He who has ^aclean hands and a ^bpure heart, Who has not ^dlifted up his soul ¹to falsehood And has not ^dsworn deceitfully. ⁵ He shall receive a ^ablessing from the LORD And ^{1b}righteousness from the God of his salvation. ⁶ ¹This is the generation of those who ^aseek Him, Who seek Your face — <i>even</i> Jacob. ²Selah.</p>	<p>1 לְדָוִד מִזְמוֹר לַיהוָה הָאָרֶץ וּמְלוֹאָהּ תִּבְּל וַיֵּשְׁבֵי בָּהּ: ² כִּי- הוּא עַל-יַמִּים יִסְדָּהּ וְעַל- נְהָרוֹת יִכּוֹנְנֶהָ: ³ מִי-יַעֲלֶה בְּהַר-יְהוָה וּמִי-יָקוּם בַּמָּקוֹם קָדְשׁוֹ: ⁴ נְקֵי כַפַּיִם וְבַר-לֵבָב אֲשֶׁר אֵלֹא-נַפְשׁוֹ לַשָּׁוְא נַפְשׁוֹ וְלֹא נִשְׁבַּע לְמַרְמָה: ⁵ יִשְׂא בְּרָכָה מֵאֵת יְהוָה וְצַדִּיקָה מֵאֱלֹהֵי יִשְׁעוֹ: ⁶ זֶה דָּוִד וְדָוִד [וְדָוִד] מִבְּקִשֵׁי פָנֶיךָ יַעֲקֹב סֵלָה: ⁷ שְׂאוּ שְׁעָרִים אֲרְאֵשׁיכֶם וְהַנִּשְׂאוּ פִתְחֵי עוֹלָם וַיָּבֹאוּ מֶלֶךְ הַכְּבוֹד: ⁸ מִי זֶה מֶלֶךְ הַכְּבוֹד יְהוָה עֲנִיזוּ וְגִבּוֹר יְהוָה וְגִבּוֹר מִלְחָמָה: ⁹ שְׂאוּ שְׁעָרִים אֲרְאֵשׁיכֶם וְשְׂאוּ פִתְחֵי עוֹלָם וַיָּבֹאוּ מֶלֶךְ הַכְּבוֹד: ¹⁰ מִי הוּא זֶה מֶלֶךְ הַכְּבוֹד יְהוָה צְבָאוֹת הוּא מֶלֶךְ הַכְּבוֹד סֵלָה: --</p>
<p>Psa. 24:7 ^aLift up your heads, O gates, And be lifted up, O ¹ancient doors, That the King of ^bglory may come in! ⁸ Who is the King of glory? The LORD ^astrong and mighty, The LORD ^bmighty in battle. ⁹ Lift up your heads, O gates, And lift <i>them</i> up, O ¹ancient doors, That the King of ^aglory may come in!</p>	<p>אֲרְאֵשׁיכֶם וְשְׂאוּ פִתְחֵי עוֹלָם וַיָּבֹאוּ מֶלֶךְ הַכְּבוֹד: ¹⁰ מִי הוּא זֶה מֶלֶךְ הַכְּבוֹד יְהוָה צְבָאוֹת הוּא מֶלֶךְ הַכְּבוֹד סֵלָה: --</p>

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Who is this King of glory?
The LORD of ^hhosts,
He is the King of glory. Selah.

References

<p>Psalm 24:1 ¹Lit <i>its fullness</i> ^a1 Cor 10:26 ^bPs 89:11</p> <p>Psalm 24:2 ^aPs 104:3, 5; 136:6</p> <p>Psalm 24:3 ^aPs 15:1 ^bPs 2:6 ^cPs 65:4</p> <p>Psalm 24:4 ¹Or <i>in vain</i> ^aJob 17:9; Ps 22:30; 26:6 ^bPs 51:10; 73:1; Matt 5:8 ^cEzek 18:15 ^dPs 15:4</p> <p>Psalm 24:5 ¹I.e. as vindicated ^aPs 115:13 ^bPs 36:10</p> <p>Psalm 24:6 ¹Or <i>Such</i> ²<i>Selah</i> may mean: <i>Pause, Crescendo</i> or <i>Musical interlude</i> ^aPs 27:4, 8</p> <p>Psalm 24:7 ¹Lit <i>everlasting</i> ^aPs 118:20; Is 26:2 ^bPs 29:2, 9; 97:6; Acts 7:2; 1 Cor 2:8</p>	<p>Psalm 24:8 ^aDeut 4:34; Ps 96:7 ^bEx 15:3, 6; Ps 76:3-6</p> <p>Psalm 24:9 ¹Lit <i>everlasting</i> ^aPs 26:8; 57:11</p> <p>Psalm 24:10 ^aGen 32:2; Josh 5:14; 2 Sam 5:10; Neh 9:6</p> <p>Author's note: <i>Selah</i> is described by Rabbi Sampson Hirsch as instructing the reader to meditate on the statement/</p>
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Targum

Psa. 24:1 Of David. A Psalm. Behold, the earth and its creatures are the LORD's, the world and those who dwell in it. ² For he set a foundation on the seas and fixed it firmly on the rivers. ³ Who will ascend the mount of the LORD's sanctuary? And who will stand in his holy place? ⁴ One with clean hands and a pure mind, who has not sworn to a lie to make himself guilty, and who has not made an oath in guile. ⁵ He will receive blessings from the presence of the LORD, and generosity from God his redemption. ⁶ This is the generation that seeks him, that looks for his countenance, O Jacob, forever! ⁷ Lift up, O sanctuary gates, your heads; and stand erect, O eternal entrances, that the glorious king may enter. ⁸ Who is this glorious king? The LORD, strong and mighty, the LORD, a mighty ruler and one who wages battle. ⁹ Lift up your heads, O gates of the Garden of Eden; and stand erect, O eternal entrances, and the glorious king will enter. ¹⁰ Who is this glorious king? The LORD Sabaoth, he is the glorious king forever.

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses are in bold.

Introduction

A goal for King David was to bring back the purity of Adam that existed before the Sin in the Garden of Eden. Ancient tradition says that Mount Moriah was the place where the LORD created Adam. Midrash Shocher Tov says that David purchased the land for the Temple from Aravna the Jebusite. David then erected a temporary altar upon which he offered sacrifices of thanksgiving (2 Samuel 24:18-25).

David intended the psalm to be recited on the day of the Temple's consecration. David believed that the presence of the LORD was in the world, and this psalm would concentrate the LORD to dwell upon the Ark of the Covenant. David was referring to the Shekinah.

Today this psalm is recited when the Torah scrolls are returned to the Ark during synagogue worship.

Verse one

הָאֶרֶץ וּמְלִואָהּ (Ha-aretz vum'loa) – means “the earth and the fullness thereof.”

This is the fundamental prerequisite for all human life and development. The fullness of the Earth belongs to the LORD since the LORD created the Earth.

By David. A psalm. The earth is the LORD's and the fullness thereof. The world of men and all that dwell in it belong to the LORD.

Verse two

The LORD formed the world upon the seas and rivers for humankind. Nations developed because of the geography that the LORD created. Seas and rivers divided people into various nations. The LORD intended for the different climatic zones on the Earth by raising the lowering the altitude of the land. The LORD set history into motion because the world's nations would have different national characteristics and peculiarities.

The LORD formed the nations of the world upon the seas and rivers, which constantly guide history.

Verse three

The psalm reminds us that the ruling force or power on the Earth is the LORD through His Shekinah. The moral Law of Malkhut rules the Earth, not humans.

Who can ascend to the mountain of the LORD, and who can stand on Mount Moriah where the Temple is to be built?

Verse four

The “clean hands” is symbolic of an inner purity where everything impure has been removed. The possession of such a person is pure so that when touched, the person remains pure. Also, the possessions this person has were not obtained by any form of ill-gotten gains. The pure heart is a person who has a pure mind that harbors no impure thoughts.

This person also never uses words for the purpose of deception. Such a person will never swear falsely to deceive other persons.

He who obtained all possessions purely through clean hands and has only pure thoughts in his heart never used falsehoods and never swore an oath falsely.

Verse five

A person who always acts, thinks, and desires to conform to all the dictates of moral Law given by the LORD can expect to receive prosperity in whatever the person does in this world.

He will receive prosperity from the LORD and kindness from the God of his salvation.

Verse six

The generation living during David's time sought after the LORD, thus, turning to Him for help and guidance. Every nation may retain its own characteristics and peculiarities. Still, each must live in conformity with the supreme divine moral Law. The reference to Jacob means "those that seek your face." This is because of the phrase **מְבַקְשֵׁי פָנַי יַעֲקֹב** (m'vach'shae panecha ya'kov). The expression is best translated as "the people of Jacob seek your countenance."

This is the generation that seeks after the LORD; the people of Jacob seek your countenance. Meditate on this verse.

Verse Seven

The order to open the gates is repeated. The first time human society did not heed the call to open the gates out of their own free will. Therefore, the author repeats this

call by using an external force. The opening of the gates allows the King of Glory to come in.

Lift up your heads, o gates, and if not, let an external force open the doors that the King of Glory may enter.

Verse eight

The King of Glory is the LORD through His Shekinah. The Shekinah wants to be a part of human existence. The Shekinah is strong and invincible. The Shekinah is ready to battle any evil in this world.

Who is the King of Glory? The invincible and strong Shekinah will win every battle that She is involved in.

Verse nine

The author repeats his demand to open the gates. The future of the people is the portals – the gates.

Lift up your heads again, O gates, lift them up to become portals of the future so that the King of Glory (the Shekinah) may come in.

Verse ten

The author asks and answers the question as to who is the King of glory. The LORD is the King of glory. The Shekinah is His vehicle to feel his presence.

Who is the King of Glory? The LORD is the King of Glory. Meditate on this verse.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

By David. A psalm. The earth is the LORD's and the fullness thereof. The world of men and all that dwell in it belong to the LORD.

The LORD formed the nations of the world upon the seas and rivers, which constantly guide history.

Who can ascend to the mountain of the LORD, and who can stand on Mount Moriah where the Temple is to be built?

He who obtained all possessions purely through clean hands and has only pure thoughts in his heart never used falsehoods and never swore an oath falsely.

He will receive prosperity from the LORD and kindness from the God of his salvation. This is the generation that seeks after the LORD; the people of Jacob seek your countenance. Meditate on this verse.

Lift up your heads, o gates, and if not, let an external force open the doors that the King of Glory may enter.

Who is the King of Glory? The invincible and strong Shekinah will win every battle that She is involved in.

Lift up your heads again, O gates, lift them up to become portals of the future so that the King of Glory (the Shekinah) may come in.

Who is the King of Glory? The LORD is the King of Glory. Meditate on this verse.

Appendix

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

